

Bilateral Open Floating Knee in a Young Functional Patient: Case Report.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Bilateral floating knee injuries represent rare, high-energy trauma patterns associated with severe soft-tissue damage, high complication rates, and challenging functional recovery. **Case presentation:** We report the case of a young male nurse who sustained bilateral complex lower-limb injuries after a high-speed motor vehicle collision, including bilateral distal femoral fractures, tibial plateau fractures, Lisfranc injuries, and multiple metatarsal fractures, consistent with bilateral Fraser type IIC floating knee injuries. Management followed a staged damage-control strategy with initial external fixation, followed by definitive internal fixation. The clinical course was complicated by postoperative infection with *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, requiring surgical debridement and antimicrobial therapy. Subsequent reconstructive procedures were performed in a staged manner. Long-term follow-up demonstrated progressive functional recovery. **Results:** After implant removal and rehabilitation, the patient achieved 110° of knee flexion and full extension, muscle strength 5/5 in all muscle groups (Daniels scale), and a "good" functional outcome according to the Karlström and Olerud score. He returned to full work activities as a nurse and resumed physical exercise, including functional training, with only intermittent pain controlled by conventional analgesics. **Conclusion:** A staged surgical strategy combined with structured rehabilitation can lead to satisfactory functional outcomes in complex bilateral floating knee injuries, even in the presence of infectious complications. Multidisciplinary management and long-term follow-up are essential for optimizing recovery.

KEYWORDS: Floating knee; young patient, Fraser classification; high-energy trauma; bilateral lower-limb fractures; staged fixation; external fixation; ORIF; Karlström and Olerud score.

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INTRODUCTION

Ipsilateral fractures of the femur and tibia are referred to as "floating knee," a term coined in 1975 by Blake and McBryde. These are characterized as complex lower limb injuries due to the anatomical and biomechanical factors involved, which are associated with dislocations and significant soft tissue trauma [1]. The force required to fracture both bones is very high, with the most frequent injury mechanism being high-energy trauma, including car accidents, falls from great heights with axial loading, extreme sports, and violent trauma.[2]

Although floating knee is considered an uncommon injury, it represents 0.3 to 2% of all fractures[1], and is associated with mortality rates of up to 8.6-10%, amputation rates of up to

27%, and vascular injury in 6% of cases.[3,4] While the exact incidence of these injuries in Latin America is unknown, multiple studies have reported that the incidence tends to be higher in adolescents and young adults, with a male-to-female ratio ranging from 2:1 to 5:1.[3]

A precise initial evaluation and management tailored to the local and general context of each patient are essential, typically applying a damage control approach.[4] All patients must be stabilized according to the ATLS protocol, and those with open fractures should be classified according to Gustilo and Anderson, requiring early antimicrobial management, emergency surgical cleaning, and temporary external fixation.[4,5]

The choice of definitive treatment remains a challenge for

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orthopedic surgeons, as the approach and osteosynthesis material selection depend on many factors, such as fracture pattern, soft tissue condition, patient age, and associated injuries. Current literature recommends first fixing the femur definitively to facilitate tibia manipulation, with the most commonly used method being the double intramedullary nail.[1,5] Due to the complexity of these injuries, multiple complications can arise in up to 33% of patients, primarily including joint stiffness, arthritis, infections, and nonunion, requiring additional surgeries in up to 46% of those affected.[1,3,6]

Although this injury is considered uncommon, the high complexity of the fractures, associated injuries, and the elevated complication rate make it a challenge even for experienced surgeons. Continued research on these injuries is essential to develop better diagnostic and treatment algorithms, which will allow for improved multidisciplinary management, as well as better functional outcomes and quality of life for patients.

CLINICAL CASE

28-year-old male patient, nurse, HIV positive, admitted to the emergency department after a car accident, crashing into a tree at approximately 90 km/h. Upon arrival, the patient was still intoxicated, disoriented in time and place, and minimally cooperative. Upon examination, he presented with a right facial hematoma, pupils reactive to light, the neck was not assessable, symmetric chest, with crackles in the left hemithorax upon auscultation, no signs of respiratory distress, rhythmic precordium, soft abdomen with no signs of peritoneal irritation. The right lower limb showed deformity at the distal femur, with a wound on the anterior aspect of the distal thigh approximately 3 x 3 cm, exposing deep tissue, and a free bone fragment from the distal femur measuring approximately 10 x 3 cm. The left lower limb had a wound on the anterior aspect of the proximal leg, approximately 5 cm, exposing deep tissue. Both feet showed ++ edema, with limited range of motion and a capillary refill time of 3 seconds.

Figure 1. Clinical images upon arrival at the emergency department. A) Wound with bone exposure at the distal third of the right thigh. B) Wound with exposure of deep tissues in the proximal third of the left leg. C) Fragment of the right femur recovered from the accident site.

The patient was stabilized in the trauma area, where intravenous fluids and antibiotics were administered. A multidisciplinary evaluation was performed, ruling out any neurological, pulmonary, or abdominal injuries requiring surgical intervention. X-rays and a computed tomography (CT) scan of both lower limbs were performed, revealing a right femur with a bone discontinuity at the distal third, with a multifragmented articular line, comminution, and 10 cm of bone loss. A tibial plateau fracture with a multifragmented lateral plateau and extension to the diaphysis. In the foot, multifragmented diaphyseal fracture of the 2nd and 3rd metatarsals was found, a neck fracture of the 4th and 5th metatarsals, as well as a fracture of the proximal phalanx of the 4th toe, and diastasis at the first intermetatarsal joint. The left lower limb showed a distal femur fracture with a simple articular and multifragmented metaphyseal fracture, a

discontinuity at the tibial plateau with a simple central articular line extending to the diaphysis. In the foot, a discontinuity at the base of the first metatarsal was observed with an articular fracture, minimally displaced.

Based on the findings, the right lower limb was diagnosed with an open distal femur fracture (Gustilo-Anderson type II) and a Schatzker VI tibial plateau fracture, constituting a Fraser type IIC floating knee injury. A Hardcastle type III Lisfranc fracture was also diagnosed, along with the previously mentioned metatarsal and phalangeal fractures. In the left lower limb, a distal femur fracture and an open Schatzker VI tibial plateau fracture (Gustilo-Anderson type II) were identified, constituting a Fraser type IIC floating knee injury, as well as a Hardcastle type I Lisfranc fracture and a fracture of the base of the first metatarsal.

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Figure 2. Initial radiographs upon arrival at the emergency department. A) Anteroposterior radiograph of both knees. B) Dorsoplantar radiograph of the right foot. C) Dorsoplantar radiograph of the left foot.

SURGICAL MANAGEMENT

First Surgical Stage

During the first surgical stage, the patient was positioned supine under balanced general anesthesia after a surgical time-out. Both lower limbs were prepared with an iodine-based solution and draped in a sterile fashion. Closed reduction was performed by gentle manipulation, followed by the placement of two Schanz screws in the anterolateral aspect of the right

thigh, one in the lateral aspect of the knee, and two in the anteromedial aspect of the tibia.

The left lower limb was then manipulated, and two Schanz screws were inserted in the anterolateral thigh and two in the anteromedial tibia. The patient was transferred from the operating room in stable condition, pending definitive osteosynthesis once appropriate fixation materials were available.

Figures 3. Postoperative radiographs. A) Anteroposterior projection of both knees. B) Lateral projection of the right knee. C) Lateral projection of the left knee.

Second Surgical Stage

During the second surgical stage, the patient was placed supine under balanced general anesthesia. After aseptic preparation, the external fixator of the right lower limb was removed. A lateral approach to the distal femur was performed through the vastus lateralis, and the fracture site was debrided and reduced using reduction clamps and provisional Kirschner wires. A 13-hole distal femoral LCP plate was applied, with fluoroscopic

confirmation of reduction. The approach was extended to the tibia, where the fracture was debrided, reduced, and fixed with a 12-hole proximal tibial LCP plate, confirming alignment in anteroposterior and lateral projections. Closed reduction and percutaneous Kirschner wire fixation of the second, third, and fourth metatarsals were performed. Estimated blood loss was 1000 mL, and two units of packed red blood cells were transfused.

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Figure 4. Postoperative radiographs after definitive fixation of the right lower limb. A) Anteroposterior view of the right femur. B) Anteroposterior view of the right knee. C) Dorsoplantar radiograph of the right foot.

Infectious Complication and Third Surgical Stage

During follow-up, the patient developed signs of right knee infection, including fever and purulent discharge. Culture revealed *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, prompting a change in the antibiotic regimen and surgical management. During the third surgical stage, 50 cc of non-fetid purulent fluid was drained, and the area was thoroughly irrigated with antibiotic solution. After completing antimicrobial treatment, follow-up cultures showed no bacterial growth, allowing planning of a fourth surgical procedure.

Fourth Surgical Stage

During the fourth surgical stage, the patient was positioned supine under balanced general anesthesia, and the external

fixator of the left lower limb was removed. An anterolateral approach to the distal femur was performed with subvastus dissection and joint capsule exposure. The articular block was reduced and temporarily stabilized with Kirschner wires. A 9-hole distal femoral LCP plate was applied using three compression screws and locking screws in the remaining holes, with fluoroscopic confirmation of reduction. The incision was extended distally for an anterolateral tibial approach, where the tibial plateau fracture was debrided, reduced, and fixed with a 12-hole proximal tibial LCP plate. Final alignment was confirmed fluoroscopically, and the wound was closed in layers.

Figure 5. Postoperative radiographs after definitive fixation of the left lower limb. A) Anteroposterior radiograph of both knees. B) Lateral projection of the left femur. C) Lateral projection of the left tibia.

Fifth Surgical Stage

The patient was discharged home due to clinical improvement and continued outpatient follow-up. Kirschner wires were removed from the right foot, and the patient was referred to physical therapy for recovery of range of motion, muscle strengthening, and gait re-education.

However, during follow-up, the patient began to experience pain at the surgical scar site on the left lower limb, as well as

tenderness over the osteosynthesis material. Therefore, a fifth surgical procedure was scheduled, during which the plates from the left distal femur and proximal tibia, as well as the proximal tibial plate on the right side, were removed. The decision was made to retain the distal femoral plate on the right limb due to the bone defect associated with the initial injury.

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Figure 6. Radiographs obtained after removal of the osteosynthesis material. A) Anteroposterior radiograph of both femurs. B) Lateral radiograph of the right femur. C) Lateral radiograph of the left femur. D) Anteroposterior radiograph of both tibias.

Functional Outcomes

After removal of the osteosynthesis material, the patient reported progressive improvement in range of motion, achieving 110° of flexion and 0° of extension, with adequate muscle strength. On physical examination, muscle strength was graded 5/5 in all muscle groups according to the Daniels scale, with no residual neurological deficit. The patient was able to return to physical activity, including functional exercises such as squats, without significant limitations.

Functional evaluation showed a “good” outcome according to the Karlström and Olerud score. The patient returned to his professional activities as a nurse at the same functional level as before the initial injury. During follow-up, he reported intermittent discomfort in the affected limb, which resolved with conventional analgesic management, and he was subsequently discharged from the service. The patient reported being functionally satisfied with the clinical outcome.

DISCUSSION

The concept of floating knee injury was first proposed by Blake and McBryde in 1975 to describe ipsilateral fractures of the femur and tibia. Floating knee injuries typically result from high-energy trauma, such as motor vehicle accidents and falls from height, and are associated with a high incidence of open fractures (59–67%) and variable fracture patterns [7]. Consistent with the literature, our patient sustained a high-energy motor vehicle accident, which is the most common mechanism reported [1,2,7].

Fraser et al. classified floating knee injuries into type I (ipsilateral diaphyseal fractures of the femur and tibia), type IIA (intra-articular tibial fracture with femoral shaft fracture), type IIB (intra-articular femoral fracture with tibial shaft fracture), and type IIC (both fractures with intra-articular involvement) [8]. Ran et al. later modified this classification in 2013 by incorporating the severity of articular comminution and associated patellar fractures, demonstrating better correlation with clinical outcomes [7]. Our patient presented with bilateral Fraser type IIC floating knees, one of

the most complex and uncommon patterns, associated with poor functional prognosis due to severe intra-articular comminution. Floating knee injuries account for approximately 0.3% to 2% of all fractures, with increasing incidence due to traffic accidents [1,9].

Demographically, these injuries predominantly affect young males, with reported male-to-female ratios up to 9:1 [7]. Dwyer et al. reported that male sex, young age, and traffic accidents were the predominant factors in floating knee injuries [5], which is consistent with our 28-year-old male patient. Floating knee injuries are frequently associated with life-threatening injuries, requiring early ATLS-based management [6]. Studies report associated head, thoracic, and abdominal injuries, with mortality rates ranging from 5% to 15% [10]. Although our patient did not present major visceral injuries, he sustained multiple foot fractures, including Lisfranc injuries, reflecting the high-energy mechanism.

Open fractures occur in up to 69% of floating knee injuries and are commonly classified using the Gustilo-Anderson system [11]. Limb salvage versus early amputation remains controversial in severe cases, and the Mangled Extremity Severity Score (MESS) can assist decision-making, with scores ≥ 7 predicting amputation [12]. The management of floating knee injuries remains controversial; however, early fixation and mobilization are generally recommended to improve outcomes [1,5]. Damage control orthopedics is recommended in unstable patients, with temporary external fixation followed by definitive fixation [13]. Our patient presented with bilateral Gustilo type II open fractures, justifying an initial damage control approach, consistent with current recommendations [13].

Surgical options include ORIF, intramedullary nailing, external fixation, arthroscopy-assisted reduction, and ligament reconstruction, depending on fracture pattern, soft tissue condition, and surgeon experience [1]. For distal femoral fractures, retrograde nailing and locking plates are commonly used. In our case, locking plate fixation was chosen due to complex intra-articular fractures, where anatomical reduction and absolute stability are priorities.

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Despite successful fixation, implant-related pain required subsequent hardware removal, which affected rehabilitation. Early complications include pneumonia, ARDS, multiorgan failure, infection, DVT, and pulmonary embolism, with DVT reported in up to 25% of patients [14]. Our patient developed a surgical site infection caused by *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, which was successfully managed with surgical debridement and targeted antibiotics. Implant-related pain requiring removal is a recognized late complication [14]. Ligament injuries are common, reported in up to 53% of floating knee cases, with long-term instability frequently observed [15,16]. Late complications include stiffness, nonunion, malunion, heterotopic ossification, implant prominence, and post-traumatic osteoarthritis [14]. Reported union times range from approximately 14–16 weeks for the femur and 22–23 weeks for the tibia, with nonunion rates up to 11% for the femur and 30% for the tibia [17]. In our case, union times were comparable to those reported, with no evidence of nonunion or malunion.

Rehabilitation after floating knee injury is prolonged and essential for functional recovery, although no standardized protocol exists. Early ankle and knee mobilization, progressive strengthening, and delayed weight-bearing are commonly recommended [18]. Our rehabilitation protocol emphasized lumbopelvic stabilization and hip strengthening to correct dynamic valgus and improve lower limb biomechanics.

Unlike many reports describing persistent functional limitations, our patient achieved favorable functional recovery, with 110° knee flexion, full extension, muscle strength 5/5 in all muscle groups (Daniels scale), return to physical activity including squats, and full return to work as a nurse. According to the Karlström and Olerud criteria, the outcome was classified as good, comparable or superior to most reported series [19,20]. Despite intermittent pain controlled with analgesics, the patient reported functional satisfaction and was discharged from follow-up.

CONCLUSION

Bilateral floating knee injuries represent a rare and highly complex orthopedic trauma pattern associated with severe soft tissue damage, high complication rates, and prolonged functional impairment. This case highlights the importance of a staged damage control orthopedic approach, followed by definitive internal fixation tailored to complex intra-articular fracture patterns. Locking plate fixation allowed adequate anatomical reduction and stability in fractures unsuitable for intramedullary nailing.

Despite early infectious complications and the need for secondary implant removal due to hardware-related symptoms, the patient achieved satisfactory fracture union and favorable functional recovery after an intensive and structured rehabilitation program. This case demonstrates that, even in severe bilateral Fraser type IIC floating knee injuries, satisfactory functional outcomes can be achieved

with multidisciplinary management, individualized surgical planning, and comprehensive rehabilitation strategies.

DECLARATION OF PATIENT CONSENT

The authors certify that the patient was informed about the use and publication of clinical information and imaging studies. Written informed consent was obtained, and the patient was informed that their name and initials would not be published, maintaining anonymity.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there were no conflicts of interest during the elaboration of this paper.

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